

DELAMINATED COMPOSITE PANELS IN COMPRESSION

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ABSTRACT

Composite plates manufactured by laminating carbon fibre epoxy prepregs are susceptible to defects such as fibre/matrix cracking and delamination between laminae (separation of adjoining plies). Delaminations are caused by either manufacturing faults or as a result of certain factors occurring during the operational life of the plate; factors such as impact by foreign bodies. The mere presence of delaminations may reduce the load-carrying capacity of the laminated structure and thus may be detrimental to the overall performance of the structural system.

In the present study a series of plates were fabricated with deliberately inbuilt delamination (in the form of peel ply) at various positions on the plate structure.

By prescribing the position and size of delaminations, their effects were studied experimentally and theoretically. In this way it was possible to determine the most detrimental position for the delamination.

In any structural design the selection of a realistic failure criterion is a vital feature. For the case of conventional metallic structures it is often sufficient to use the ultimate tensile, compression or shear stress to describe failure. With composites such a method is in many cases inadequate to predict structural failure.

The paper summarises the results of a theoretical and experimental study of the effects of delamination on the stability behaviour of composite panels and investigates the failure modes of laminated panels in compression.

KEYWORDS: Buckling; Delamination; Failure criterion; Laminated plate theory; Postbuckling.

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NOTATION

x, y	cartesian co-ordinates
a, b, t	length, width and thickness of sublaminates respectively
$A_{ij}^*, B_{ij}^*, D_{ij}^*$	extensional, coupling and bending stiffnesses of sublaminates respectively
N_{xs}, N_{ys}, N_{xys}	resultant stresses acting on sublaminates
M_{xs}, M_{ys}, M_{xys}	resultant moments acting on sublaminates
w	out-of-plane deflections
e	ratio of buckle half wavelength to width
U, U_{cr}	end shortening and critical end shortening of panel respectively
N, N_{cr}	applied load and buckling load of panel respectively
EPS_{xm}	membrane strain in the x-direction
EPS_{ym}	membrane strain in the y-direction
EPS_{xb}	bending strain in the x-direction
EPS_{yb}	bending strain in the y-direction
EPS_{xtot}	total strain in the x-direction

1.0 INTRODUCTION

A laminate with an interply delamination located just beneath the panel surface is shown in Fig 1. A number of researchers such as Konishi¹, Shivakumar & Whitcomb², Whitcomb³ and Chai & Babcock⁴ have looked into the behaviour of such a laminate. A variety of approaches were used.

A simple model based on the instability behaviour of the sublaminates in relation to the base laminate will be presented in this paper. The development of a model of a panel with interply delamination is illustrated in Fig 1 and its expected stress-strain behaviour is described in Fig 2.

The instability of the sublaminates can occur either before or after the laminate buckles. These are shown in Fig 1(b) and Fig 1(b¹) respectively. An assumption is then made at this stage when the sublaminates buckle that the length of the delamination propagates across and along the laminate as shown in Fig 1(c) and Fig 1(c¹). The ply/plices associated with the sublaminates is then assigned zero stiffness to yield the final model of Fig 1(d). Hence the applied load will be transferred to the base laminate up to failure. This assumption may ensure a truly conservative theoretical solution, i.e. a lower bound solution.

Fig 2 presents the anticipated stress-strain behaviour of the above panel. Curve 1 shows the behaviour when the sublaminates buckling load is higher than the 'reduced modulus' laminate buckling load, before the overall instability has occurred. If the buckling load of the sublaminates is less than the buckling load of the 'reduced' laminate then curve 2 is to be expected.

Curves 3 and 4 show the expected stress-strain behaviour when the instability of the sublaminates occurs after the overall instability has taken place. Fig 2 therefore clearly summarises the degree of severity of load reduction for panels with delamination. Clearly this depends on the delamination geometry and its location.

The sublaminat model The sublaminat can be modelled as a rectangular plate subjected to a biaxial stress state as shown in Fig 3. If the case of fully fixed boundary conditions on all edges is considered, the biaxial stress state on the sublaminat can be evaluated using the large deflection analytical approach of Ref⁵ combined with the classical lamination theory.

The total strain energy in the plate consists of the potential energy lost in the sublaminat system and the strain energy of bending in the sublaminat system.

Postulating a deflection function and substituting into the total strain energy expression and minimising with respect to the deflection coefficient yields the buckling coefficient.

The resultant load acting biaxially on the sublaminat can be analysed from the classical lamination approach coupled with the large deflection analysis of the laminate in uniaxial compression. The stresses in each individual layer of the laminate can then be obtained, together with the stress resultants.

There will be a stress re-distribution across the width and along the length of the panel after initial instability. Thus the resultant stresses acting on the sublaminat will not be uniform, and this complicates the analysis. Since the geometry can be assumed to be very small in comparison to the laminate, the stress resultant acting on the sublaminat can be averaged and assumed to be acting uniformly. The interaction relationship of the sublaminat to the panel as a whole can be investigated by incorporating the sublaminat instability criterion into the large deflection equations developed in Ref⁵ for laminated panels.

2.0 SELECTION OF A FAILURE CRITERION

The selection of a suitable failure criterion for composites has become one of the most difficult and challenging topics in composite structural design. The inherent heterogeneous and anisotropic nature of composite materials represents a novel challenge in the development of a failure criterion in which all failure modes and their interactions are adequately accounted for. The ideal failure criterion is clearly one which requires a minimum of material testing but differentiates the different failure modes. As will be seen later this is one of many factors which hinders the progress of an ideal failure criterion.

The failure criteria of composite laminated structures are usually based on the macromechanical failure rather than the micromechanical failure. The effect of degradation on the structure due to the presence of flaws or defects is characterised in the micromechanical approach. Though such factors contribute to failure, they are not considered as primary factors when describing failure in a global sense. Therefore in this respect the failure modes can either be fibre dominated, matrix dominated or a combination of both. Numerous proposals for the failure criteria have been made.

These include the Tsai-Hill criterion, the Hoffman's criterion and the Tsai-Wu Tensor criterion. All these criteria are an extension of the yield criterion for the isotropic case. There are of course many other failure criteria available in the literature as well, most of them are modified forms of the quadratic interaction criterion.

For material of transverse isotropy in plane stress, the Tsai-Hill failure criterion is simplified to this familiar form which is very frequently used to describe failure of a fibre reinforced layer:

$$\left(\frac{\sigma_1}{X}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_2}{Y}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{\sigma_1\sigma_2}{X^2}\right) + \left(\frac{\tau_{12}}{S}\right)^2 = 1$$

The Tsai-Hill criterion however does not account for the different strengths in tension and compression. Hoffman⁷ in 1967 added two extra linear terms to the original Hill's equation to take into account these strength differences. In its simple form Hoffman's criterion is:

$$\frac{\sigma_1^2}{X_c X_t} + \frac{\sigma_2^2}{Y_c Y_t} - \frac{\sigma_1 \sigma_2}{X_c X_t} + \frac{X_c - X_t}{X_c X_t} \sigma_1 + \frac{Y_c - Y_t}{Y_c Y_t} \sigma_2 = 1$$

where the subscript *c* refers to compression and *t* refers to tension. There are several obvious attractive features of this criterion. The strength parameters can be obtained by simple tests. Interaction between failure modes is treated and a single criterion to describe all regions of failure in the stress space is used.

The strength behaviour of each ply in the laminate is determined by assuming that a plane state of stress exists for each ply regardless of its fibre orientation and position within the laminate. The stresses in each ply are calculated and transformed to the material axes of the ply, then a fail safe design on a ply by ply basis is determined. If a failed ply has been analysed then an appropriate first-ply-failure assessment can be made and the behaviour after first ply is examined.

After first-ply-failure, the structure may still be able to carry additional loads and several ways to study their behaviour have been introduced. One of the methods was published by Hahn and Tsai⁸. This approach is based on the assumption that the failed ply/plies remains in the structure as a volume entity but that it can no longer carry any load. This method has been shown to give a conservative solution to the failure analysis.

3. EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION

An extensive experimental investigation was carried out to ascertain the validity of the theoretical analysis and to provide confidence in the conclusions reached.

A total of 20 test panels, in 5 separate batches, were tested. Each test panel being nominally 1.75 mm thick with 57.1% of the layers at 0°, 14.3% at 90°, and 28.6% at ±45°. The geometries of the panels are tabulated in Table 1 and all test panels have the detailed lay-up of [+45/0/0/90/0/-45/0]s.

The reinforcing material was manufactured by CIBA-GEIGY, Grafil XA-S unidirectional carbon fibre in 914C Fibredux epoxy resin. Thickness variation in the final panels was very small being 1.75 + 0.05 mm. It should be noted however that test panels SCB3-1 to SCB3-4 have nominal measured thicknesses of 1.83 mm. The material properties used for the test panels are the compression properties commonly used in the industry: $E_{11}=130\text{GPa}$, $E_{22}=9\text{GPa}$, $G_{12}=4.8\text{GPa}$ and $\nu_{12}=0.28$.

The panels had built-in delaminations the positions of which are as indicated in Table 2. The delaminations were simulated by using 2 thicknesses of A4000 release film cut to the appropriate shape and interleaved between the plies during the impregnation process. An analysis performed by British Aerospace plc using COMPLAN (a finite element method programme, see Rajan⁹) predicted the areas of maximum direct stress and areas of maximum interlaminar shear stress. Based on these predictions, delaminations were prescribed to coincide with these critical areas.

The last batch of test panels SCB3-1 to 4 had delaminations placed taking into consideration among other things the findings of Buskell et al¹⁰. They concluded that regardless of the

stacking sequence delaminations were always found to occur near the middle surface of the buckle nodal line. These areas coincide with the areas of maximum interlaminar shear stress predicted by COMPLAN.

The test set-up is shown in Fig 4 with full details given in Ref⁹.

The panels were fitted into aluminium end blocks using araldite and loads were applied at this end. The long edges were supported on adjustable knife edges which simulated simply supported conditions. The test panel overhung the knife edges by 6.5 mm and this narrow strip is assumed not to influence the buckling behaviour. During testing these knife edges were coated with grease to reduce the friction effect and thus ensure that the sides of the panel were 'free to wave' in plane and remain stress free.

The test panel was then subjected to a very small load to allow the panel to settle into the test rig and take up any movement between the components of the rig. This load was then removed and the dial gauge reading was zeroed and the strain gauges were balanced for the zero reading. The load was then increased in incremental steps, with smaller steps in the critical buckling region and in the critical failure stage. Each load step was held for a short period of time to enable the required readings to be recorded before the next load increment.

The load was applied within the elastic range and removed to allow the panel to further settle into the rig. Also to check for any irregularities in the readings especially the strain gauge readings. After the checking, and several loading and unloading tests, the panel was then tested to failure. Since the loading machine had a displacement controlled process collapse of the panel was denoted as a sudden reduction in load.

4. EXPERIMENTAL FINDINGS

Due to space limitation only sample results are presented.

The results for load-end shortening behaviour for test panels SCB2-4 and SCB2-4A are shown in Fig 5. These panels have delamination between the 11/12th ply sited at the edge of the buckle node. Agreement is observed to be reasonable. A lower bound theoretical solution prevails. The experimental data shows the delamination has not affected the postbuckling strength but theory predicts a much lower postbuckling stiffness due to the effect of delamination.

The failure analysis of laminated panels is investigated with the two criteria referred to earlier. They are used to describe failure in each individual layer of the laminate. Fig 6 indicates the values obtained for test panels SCB2-1A through SCB2-4A.

In this latter case the theoretical analysis gives conservative results even for the ultimate failure load prediction. In other cases however conservative prediction in the first-ply failure only are obtained.

A summary of the failure characteristics given in Fig 7 shows that in most cases failure occurs across the buckle nodal line whereas the Tsai-Hill and Hoffman criteria predict that failure occurs at a buckle peak. This is somewhat contradictory and shows that these criteria do not predict accurately the failure modes in the postbuckling range for the laminates tested. The authors are doubtful if the other forms of the quadratic interaction criterion can be used here. Current research on a postbuckling failure criterion based on the maximum interlaminar shear stress by Buskell et al¹⁰ seems promising.

4. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

The analytical approach for panels with interply delaminations is shown in all cases to be conservative. The approach is at its first stage of development. The interlaminar stresses at ply interface will affect the instability of the sublaminates and should thus be one of the factors to be included in the future. The different shapes of delaminations such as circular and semi-circular shapes should also be studied.

The failure prediction for panels with a length to width ratio of 3.82 is unconservative even for the first-ply-failure solution. For panels with a length to width ratio of 5.09 conservative failure prediction is obtained in many cases. Failure in all cases is predicted to occur at the top ply at a buckle peak, and in the experimental results (apart from the end problems) failure usually occurred across a buckle node. Thus a search for a suitable failure criterion capable of predicting the failure modes of laminates subjected to compression in the postbuckling range should still be pursued.

5. REFERENCES

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Test panels	Width (mm)	Length (mm)	Thickness (mm)	b/t
SCB1-1 SCB1-2 SCB1-3 SCB1-4 SCB1-5 SCB1-6	120	458	1.75	68.57
SCB1-1A SCB1-2A	120	458	1.75	68.57
SCB2-1 SCB2-2 SCB2-3 SCB2-4	90	458	1.75	51.43
SCB2-1A SCB2-2A SCB2-3A SCB2-4A	90	458	1.75	51.43
SCB3-1 SCB3-2 SCB3-3 SCB3-4	90	458	1.83	51.43

TABLE 1 Dimensions of the test panels

Test panels	Location of prescribed interply delamination
SCB1-2	Between the 7/8th ply near the edges of the buckle nodal line.
SCB1-4	Between the 3/4th ply, and between the 11/12th ply near the centre of the buckle node.
SCB1-5	Between the 7/8th ply near the centre of the buckle nodal line at the panel centre.
SCB1-6	Between the 3/4th ply, and between the 11/12th ply near the centre of buckle node.
SCB2-3 SCB2-3A	Between the 3/4th ply, and between the 11/12th ply near the edges of buckle peak.
SCB1-3 SCB2-4 SCB2-4A	Between the 3/4th ply, and between the 11/12th ply near the edges of buckle node.
SCB3-1	Between the 6/7th ply near the centre of the buckle nodal line.
SCB3-2	Between the 6/7th ply near the centre of the buckle nodal line at the panel centre.
SCB3-3	Between the 6/7th ply near the edges of the buckle nodal line at the panel centre.
SCB3-4	Between the 6/7th ply near the edges of the buckle nodal line.

All other panels not mentioned here are with no prescribed delaminations.

TABLE 2 Description of areas of prescribed delaminations in the test panels.

Panel geometries		Load at First-Ply-Failure (N/N_{σ})		Ultimate Failure Load (N/N_{σ})	
a/b	t (mm)	Hoffman (HFPF)	Tsai-Hill (TFPF)	Hoffman (HUF)	Tsai-Hill (TUF)
458/120	1.75	6.70	7.15	7.48	7.42
458/90	1.75	3.39	3.57	4.37	4.39
458/90	1.83	3.06	3.26	3.94	3.93

TABLE 3 Summary of the theoretical failure loads.

Figure 1 A model of a laminate with delamination and subjected to compression

Figure 4 An illustration of the overall test set-up

Figure 5 Load-End Shortening Behaviour (SCB2-4 & 4A)

Figure 6 Failure description of test panels SCB2-1A to 4A

Figure 7 Experimental failures of the test panels

